

PROFICIENCY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS IN MATHEMATICS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 5

Pages: 523-537

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1776

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11095066

Manuscript Accepted: 04-05-2024

Proficiency and Academic Achievement of Grade 7 Students in Mathematics

Riza S. Berrame*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

One of the most ultimate goals of every math teacher and the school is to improve the level of proficiency and academic achievement of low performing students in Mathematics. This study focused mainly on the proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics. The research design used is Quantitative Descriptive Comparative and Correlational technique. In 96 sample respondents, 48 were males and 48 females. Stratified random sampling was employed in the selection of respondents per strata. Based on the results, the level of proficiency of the students was low/below standard and the level of academic achievement of the students was satisfactory. It showed that the mean difference of the proficiency and academic performance of students when grouped according to sex was not significant at 0.05 alpha level, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. However, there existed a significant relationship between the proficiency and academic achievement of students in Mathematics. It revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected. It is concluded that the proficiency of Grade 7 students had a great impact on the academic achievement in Mathematics. Based on the results of the study, a Development Program in Mathematics was made to improve the proficiency and academic achievement of students.

Keywords: *proficiency, academic achievement, sex, descriptive-correlational, central visayas, Philippines*

Introduction

All subjects are essential for learners and educators, but mathematics education serves a general purpose of school to develop human beings mentally, healthy, and physically. It makes people creative and responsible (Niss, 2016). Mathematics education enables learners to meet society demands for adequately qualified and flexible or pliable work force. The primary aim of teaching Mathematics is to develop problem-solving skills among the students (Krishnan & Devanesan, 2017). One of the factors leading to this aim is mathematical proficiency.

Asmara (2013) said that to have the ability to think critically, creatively, logically, and systematically students must have mathematical proficiency. For years educators have searched for ways to teach mathematics more effectively to all students. Math education enables learners to meet society demands for a competent and flexible work force (Niss, 2016). School officials try hard to improve the educational achievement of all its students so that all can try to reach the highest level of achievement. Although government and local community together strive to change the situation of education but still there are some problems in front of education and its improvements.

In the United States of America (USA), students have trailed other industrialized nations in mathematics proficiency and achievement (Rave and Golightly, 2014). This study suggests that knowledge of basic math may be at the core of these math proficiency deficits. Mathematics mastery is the ability to respond to the four basic math operations (Musti-Rao et al., 2015; Nelson et al., 2016).

Students acquire mathematical mastery at different rates and therefore need varying degrees of practice before achieving mathematical proficiency (Burns et al., 2015). Even in the most recent international comparisons, students in the US ranked 40th out of 72 countries (OECD, 2016), an issue that has prevailed for decades despite a vast body of research that has shown the ways to teach mathematics well (Schoenfeld, 2002; Boaler, 2016). Low mathematics achievement is not the only problem that faces the US—math anxiety is widespread among school children and the general population (Ashcraft and Krause, 2007; Foley et al., 2017).

In Asia, it is viewed as one of the most critical subjects wherein students are encouraged to study the discipline (Leatham & Peterson, 2010; Ronis, 2008). Thus, it is in this view that in most Asian countries, guiding practices on children's mathematics achievements are quite more vigorous (Wei & Dzung, 2014).

Mathematics proficiency has become a more significant focus in K-12 education with the introduction of the Common Core Standards (CCSS; Porter, McMaken, Hwang, & Yang, 2011). While multiple factors contribute to poor mathematics performance, the inability of students to fluently solve fundamental mathematics problems plays a significant role (Bryant et al., 2015; Kanive, Nelson, Burns, & Ysseldyke, 2014). Students who struggle to solve fundamental computational problems will, in turn, struggle with complex and higher-level mathematical skills (Geary, Hoard, Nugent, & Bailey, 2013). Without a strong conceptual understanding and foundational fluency, it is not easy to progress through higher levels of mathematics (Geary, 2014; 2011).

Mathematics achievement, on the other hand, is a subject area of particular concern in this nation. (Boaler, 2016) said that there are myths that hold students back daily and reduce their learning and achievement significantly. Some people are born with a "math brain," and some are not, and that high achievement is only available to some students.

In 2012, DepEd embraced the K-12 curriculum, which means that the Philippine Basic Education observes the kindergarten plus 12

years to complete its Basic Education Program (DepEd, 2012). This move is taken because of the poor quality of the Philippine Basic Education as reflected by the low achievement scores of Filipino students in the National Achievement Test (NAT 2015) and the international test known as the Third International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) (Tatsuoka, Corter, & Tatsuoka, 2004; DepEd, 2012). (Jaudinez, 2019) claimed that low performance of students had been attributed to students' lack of mastery of basic skills, stigma, and language used.

The mathematics performance of Filipino students in national achievement and international achievement has been consistently low, and the situation at local levels is similar (Aguinaldo, 2001; Ayap, 2007; Balbalosa, 2010). The scenarios mentioned earlier have brought the researcher to develop a study on determining the proficiency and academic achievement, specifically the Grade 7 students on why meeting the target of a hundred percent of its population to meet the 75% proficiency criterion remained unachievable.

Unfortunately, with the threat of COVID-19, achieving the said target and delivering the curriculum has become a challenging task to the teachers to prepare the school in a different set-up, the New Normal, while making education available and thriving, even in the most challenging time. In this new normal set-up, most students are left with self-learning modules (SLMs) designed to freely choose when and where to learn without direct contact with their teachers. Thus, hindering students from attaining mathematical proficiency and achievement.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of the study was to determine the proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics. Specifically, this aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex?
2. What is the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when grouped according to sex?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics and when grouped according to sex?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, research locale, population and sample size, sampling technique, data gathering procedure, data gathering instrument, and statistical tools used in computation and interpretation of data.

Research Design

This study employed the Descriptive Comparative and Correlational Research Design to determine the correlation of proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics. According to (Sousa, Driessnack, and Mendes, 2007), correlational designs involve the systematic investigation of the nature of relationships, or associations between and among variables, rather than direct cause-effect relationships. Harcourt (2020) mentioned a statistical measure of a relationship between two or more variables, indicating how one variable may predict another.

Participants

The research respondents of this study were the ninety-six (96) Grade 7 students of one of the Public Secondary Schools in Bais City, Province of Negros Oriental.

Table 1 shows the population of one hundred twenty-seven (127) Grade 7 students, of which 63 were males and 64 females.

Below further showed the distribution of the number of respondents with corresponding percentages.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Sex</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>
Male	63	48	50%
Female	64	48	50%
Total	127	96	100%

The sample computation was done using Yamane's formula with a margin of error of 5% and a 95% confidence level. The Yamane's or commonly called Slovin's, formula calculates the number of samples required when the population is too large to sample every member (Ellen, 2020) directly. It works for simple random sampling.

The sample was chosen using stratified random sampling-proportionate allocation for the sex. Wheelan (2014) states that stratified random sampling is used when the population is divided into strata (male and female or education level) and any stratum included when taking the sample.

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a researcher-made based on the Most Essentials Learning Competencies (MELC) to determine the level of proficiency.

The instrument was composed of a 40-item teacher-made proficiency test in Mathematics which covers topics from first to third quarters to determine the proficiency level of the Grade 7 students in Mathematics. The grades of the Grade 7 students in Mathematics from first to third quarters as the secondary data were taken from the school record, specifically in Form 10 (Permanent Record).

To make sure that the instrument would be an accurate and effective one, it was subjected to validity and reliability tests before the conduct of the study.

Validity

Validity refers to how accurately a method measures what it is intended to measure (Middleton, 2020). If research has high validity, it produces results corresponding to fundamental properties, characteristics, and variations in the physical or social world.

The questionnaire of this study underwent content validity, a type of validity in which the suitability of the items in the questionnaire was verified. The validators were looking into the alignment of the questions with the objectives and scope of the investigation. The questionnaire was validated by 10 experts in the field of mathematics.

The criterion used by the jurors was the Lawshe content validity ratio (CVR). The CVR (content validity ratio) proposed by Lawshe (1975) is a linear transformation of a proportional level of agreement on how many experts within a panel rate an item essentially calculated in the following way. He developed the CVR formula to rate how essential a purpose, product, or employee is to the needs at hand. Out of 80 items that covered the MELC in Grade 7 Mathematics from the first to the third quarter, all the items were retained. The Content Validity Index (CVI) of the research instrument validated by the ten experts resulted in 0.93. (See Appendix F)

Reliability

Reliability refers to whether one gets the same answer by using an instrument to measure something more than once (Dudovskiy, 2018). In simple terms, research reliability is the degree to which a research method produces stable and consistent results. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the validated 60 items teacher-made test was subjected to item analysis. Twenty were rejected, and 40 items were retained (see Appendix G). When computed using the Kuder Richardson 21(KR 21) for internal consistency, it resulted in 0.73, which is acceptable. The researcher administered the teacher-made questionnaire to 30 Grade 7 students who were not included in the samples in the same secondary high school to ascertain the reliability.

Procedure

The researcher sent a letter to the school principal asking permission to conduct the study to the grade 7 students. A consent letter for the parents of the respondents was distributed to affirm that the inclusion of their child is part of the investigation. A letter was also sent to the barangay captain where the students resided, asking permission to allow the researcher to use the barangay hall facility in the conduct of the study following the minimum health protocols of the COVID-19. When approval of the requests was granted, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents. Data gathering was done for four weeks to ensure that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the study. After the survey, the researcher collected, organized, collated, encoded, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the data. In the same way, the researcher sought approval from the record section to get access to the quarterly grades of the respondents in Mathematics.

Statistical Treatment

The following were the descriptive and inferential statistics used by the researcher to answer questions proposed in this study: To determine the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when taken as a whole and when grouped according to sex, mean and standard deviation were used. To obtain the mean interpretation of the result on students' level of proficiency, the guide was used.

Mean Percentage Score	Interpretation	Verbal Description
96 – 100	Mastered	Students demonstrated high performance.
86 – 95	Closely Approximating Mastery/ Superior	Students' performance is close to approximating Mastery Level.
75 – 85	Meeting Standard	Students having this MPS scale is advised to engage in more enrichment activities
66 – 74	Moving Toward Mastery	Students having this MPS scale is required to submit themselves to remediation programs
35 – 65	Low/Below Standard	Students having this MPS scale is required to submit themselves to intensive remediation programs
0 – 34	Poor/Very Low	Reteaching the topics to these students is recommended.

Adopted by DepEd's Key Indicator of the Mean Percentage Score and the Least Learned Competencies

To determine the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex, mean and standard deviation were utilized. To obtain the mean interpretation of the result on the level of academic achievement of students, the guide was utilized.

<i>Grading Scale</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
90-100	Outstanding	Students obtaining this scale have demonstrated the utmost mastery level of the set standards.
85-89	Very Satisfactory	Students obtaining this scale have demonstrated nearing towards the utmost mastery level of the set standards and requires enrichment activities.
80-84	Satisfactory	Students performing at this level have met the required minimum standards and requires enhancement activities.
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Students performing at this level have met the required minimum passing standards and requires remediation.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Students performing at this level have not met the required passing standards and requires repeating the subject.

Adopted by DepEd's Learners Information System DO 13, s.2014

To determine the significant difference in the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when grouped according to sex, a t-test of independent means was used.

To determine the significant difference in the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when grouped according to sex, Mann-Whitney U-test was used for non-parametric data.

Correlation was utilized to determine the significant relationship between the proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics.

Ethical Considerations

The principles of ethical conduct below represent an overview gleaned from many sources were strictly observed:

Social Value. Covid 19 had a significant effect on the way we live today and has limited us from doing our normal routine. Assuring the safety of the participants in this study, full adherence to government-mandated health regulations was observed. This was one of the prerequisites for the study's completion.

Informed Consent. Informed consent was given to the respondents' parents to affirm that their child's inclusion is part of the investigation.

Vulnerability of respondents. Information on students' academic achievement and proficiency in Mathematics was held confidential, and data analysis results were used for research and educational purposes.

Risk and Benefits. The researcher should make sure that the respondents observed the minimum health standards in the conduct and retrieval of the survey questionnaire. The respondents benefitted from the result of the study, as the results may serve as the basis for program planning to improve the students' proficiency in mathematics.

Privacy and confidentiality. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, personal data that might compromise the respondent's identity was not divulged to the public and any information without the respondents' consent. Passcodes protected spreadsheets that were shared with the researcher to protect the confidentiality of the data.

Justice. Stratified random sampling was used to provide equal opportunity for all Grade 7 students to be selected. The results of the study were given to school administrators and teachers.

Transparency. The purpose of the study was adequately communicated with the school administrators and respondents. All relevant information related to the conduct of the study was laid down properly.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher had taught Secondary Mathematics for 14 years in Bais City, Negros Occidental, and has completed the academic requirements leading to the Master of Arts in Education Major in Mathematics.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. The findings of the investigation were divided into two parts; the descriptive and inferential data based on the statement of the problem.

Table 2 presents the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex. It was found out that both males and females belong to low/below standard with the mean of 50.42; SD=20.11 and 52.29; SD=21.28 respectively, and when taken as a whole with the mean of 51.35; SD=20.62 also belongs to low/below standard.

It was noticed that the measure of the spread of scores within the set of data when grouped according to sex was spread out over an extensive range of values. This means that the scores of Grade 7 students in Mathematics proficiency were extremes.

Table 2. *Level of Proficiency of Grade 7 Students In Mathematics When Taken As A Whole And When Grouped According to Sex*

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	50.42	20.11	Low/Below Standard
	Female	48	52.29	21.28	Low/Below Standard
Taken as a Whole		96	51.35	20.62	Low/Below Standard

The result implied that the low/below standard level of proficiency of the Grade 7 students needs intensive remediation. According to Chin (2020), this result was brought about by New Normal modular distance learning education of the Department of Education with minimal to almost non-existent supervision from teachers.

This result is also supported by (Wu) 2008, which showed a low level of conceptual understanding and strategic competence in mathematics of students. In addition, findings from South Africa had revealed that the level of mathematical proficiency of Grade 7 classes was very low (Ally (2011). The findings from Malaysia showed that the level of mathematical proficiency in three areas of conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, and strategic competence for 14-year-old students was very low (Khairani & Nordin, 2011). According to Ally and Christiansen (2013), opportunities to develop mathematical mastery are plentiful in South Africa. However, they are often of poor quality because basic Mathematics concepts are not adequately grasped, and engaging in adaptive reasoning, hardly have any opportunities to develop a productive disposition. They are rarely allowed to engage in problem-solving that could develop their strategic thinking.

Table 3. *Level of Academic Achievement of Grade 7 Students in Mathematics When Taken as a Whole and When grouped according to Sex*

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	80.60	3.45	Satisfactory
	Female	48	81.92	3.92	Satisfactory
Taken as a Whole		96	81.26	3.73	Satisfactory

Table 3 shows the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in mathematics when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex. When taken as a whole, Grade 7 students' mathematics achievement was meeting standard with the mean score of 81.26; SD=3.73. Moreover, female students with a mean score of 81.92; SD=3.92 and male students with a mean score of 80.60; SD=3.45 both interpreted as meeting the standard. Students' academic achievement in mathematics belongs to the range of satisfactory, which implied that students have a moderate or average level of learning. This indicated that Grade 7 students performing at this level have met the required minimum standards and requires enhancement activities.

Contrary to results from PISA 2012, more than one in four 15-year-old students in OECD countries end their schooling without having attained a baseline level of proficiency in at least one of the three core subjects PISA assesses: reading, mathematics, and science. Recently in Botswana, teachers have been blamed for low students' performance and unjustified professional misconduct (The Botswana Gazette, 2013).

Another study conducted by the Ministry of Education (2016) recognizes that, despite an increase in the number of students who qualify for tertiary education between 2007 and 2012, performance in mathematics and science at secondary schools in Ghana has been lacking. Student's performance in Mathematics in Tanzania, despite being the core and compulsory subject, had been low for several years in Certificate of Secondary Education Examinations (CSEE) (Kita, 2004, Mlozi, Kaguo & Nyamba, 2013, URT, 2008 and SEDP, 2004). Thus, it is in this context that mathematical knowledge is fundamental. However, mathematical performance remains down to the mark, leading towards the poor academic achievement (M.S. De Caro, 2010).

Table 4. *Significant Difference in the Level of Proficiency of Grade 7 Students in Mathematics*

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Sd	T-test	df	P-Value	Decision	Significance @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Sex	Male	48	50.42	20.11	-0.44	94	.658	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Female	48	52.29	21.28					

Table 4 reveals the significant difference in the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in mathematics.

Using the Independent t-test analysis in computing for the mean difference when grouped according to sex, the result showed that the computed p-value of 0.658 was more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. This meant no significant difference in the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in mathematics. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

The findings implied that sex is not a factor that affects the level of proficiency of Grade 7 students in Mathematics. The non-significant result in this table was in agreement with the previous study findings (Arigbabu & Mji, 2004; Awofala & Anyikwa, 2014; Facade, Nneji, Awofala & Awofala, 2012) in advanced mathematics and numeracy among preservice mathematics teachers and adult learners but ran contrary to other Int J Res Educ Sci 498 previous findings (Awofala, 2008a; Awofala, 2008b; Awofala, 2010; Awofala, 2011; Akinsola & Awofala, 2009; Ozofor, 2001; Ogunkunle, 2007) which revealed the existence of significant gender differences in mathematics. On the other hand, the significant gender effect on secondary students' performance in mathematics re-echoed the

dwindling parlance that males were better in mathematics than females. Samuelsson (2010) found no significant effect of gender on each of the dimensions of mathematical proficiency. The implication of the present study findings regarding gender is that gender differences in mathematical proficiency are no longer essential and are dissipating, but subtle differences might still exist in performance in mathematics.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Level of Academic Achievement of Grade 7 Students in Mathematics

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Mean-Whitney U	z	P-value	Decision	Significance @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Sex	Male	48	80.0	945	-1.52	.127	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
	Female	48	81.0					

Table 5 provides the Mann-Whitney U-test analysis for non-parametric data on the significant difference in the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in mathematics when grouped according to sex. It revealed that the computed U-test was 945, and the p-value of 0.127 was more significant than the 0.05 level of significance of the test. This meant no significant difference in the level of academic achievement of Grade 7 students in mathematics. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

The result indicated that the variable sex was not a determinant in the achievement of students in Mathematics. Students can get high grades despite their sex. This result agrees with some prior research on the differences in classroom performance between male and female students. Others showed mixed results. While no differences existed in some studies, others showed significant differences (Dania PO, 2014). Gender differences in achievement have been examined for some time resulting in a substantial body of literature (Awofala, Adeneye & Nneji (2011) & Amosun (2011), Apata (2011); Dania (2014); Agbaje & Alake, (2014); Atovigba et al., (2012). Some of these researchers pointed out that there is no significant gender difference in students' academic achievement and retention in various subjects, while others found significant differences between the boys and the girls performing better.

Table 6. Significant Relationship in the Proficiency and Academic Achievement of Grade 7 Students in Mathematics

Variable	R	p-value	Decision	Significance @ $\alpha = 0.05$
Proficiency and Academic achievement	.717**	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between the proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics. It could be deduced from the data that there was a significant relationship between proficiency and academic achievement, as shown in the computed r-value of 0.717 at 0.001 p-value, which was lesser than the 0.05 significant level of the test. Therefore, the hypothesis as stated that there was no significant relationship was rejected.

The findings implied that proficiency was significantly related to the academic achievement of students in Mathematics. It simply meant that the higher or lower the proficiency level of students could have something to do with students' success in Mathematics.

In a recent study done by Ghenghesh (2014), it was found that student's proficiency was significantly correlated with their overall academic achievement for most models in subjects taught at all levels of the educational system (Cimmiyotti, 2013).

Conclusion

Based on the outcome of the study, the following conclusions have come up by the researcher.

The Grade 7 students have the poor ability in Mathematics, and they need intensive remediation to improve their proficiency level. Poor ability in solving was an indication that students lacked critical and problem-solving skills necessary to solve real-life problems, and lack of these does not indicate quality in modules offered (Agbelekale, 2010). Thus, acquiring mathematics knowledge and skills is essential (Bryant, 2009; Berch & Mazzocco, 2007).

Parental support has a direct influence on learners' achievements. In the United States, those students had better achievement because of parental support for mathematics activities without any gender difference (Gray, 2016). Moreover, students' level of proficiency in Mathematics, and student's academic achievement in mathematics did not relate significantly to respondent's profiles by sex. It was supported by the study of Cordova & Tan (2018) that sex was not a determinant in the proficiency and achievement of students academically. Male and female students learn knowledge without any difference.

Lastly, the proficiency level of Grade 7 students had a great impact on how students achieve in Mathematics. Ghenghesh (2014) found out that student's proficiency was significantly correlated with their overall academic achievement. The global COVID-19 pandemic has had huge disruptive effects on everyday life, specifically in the educational system. For schools, students, and parents, the impact of closed schools and children stuck at home with little or no access to learning, the effect has been devastating. Experts estimate that a whole year of learning could be lost, meaning a whole cohort of students could be permanently lagging in their learning.

Confronting with this scenario, the result of the study significantly showed consequences in the proficiency and academic achievement of the students.

Therefore, recommendations to this endeavor were enumerated to create opportunities for the improvement of students' performance in school. Parents and teachers are encouraged to avoid the sex stereotype in considering students' mathematical proficiency and academic achievement. Both male and female students should be given equal chances of proving themselves according to their output.

There is a strong need for parents' guidance and involvement in the learning process of their child/children, especially in answering the modules at home. Parents shall exert a positive influence on their children's mathematical performance because parental support directly influences learners' achievements.

The school must provide comprehensive online or face to face orientations and talks for parents on the following concerns: proper use of modules, open heart acceptance and commitment to this New Normal learning modality, positive tips in dealing with their child/children in learning at home, and how to cope with mental health issues to ameliorate students tangible evidence in Mathematics using the modules.

The Mathematics Coordinator and teachers may evaluate the effectiveness of the appropriateness of the instructional module to students of the remote location. In addition, teachers, school administrators, and parents will collaborate and endeavor to attain outstanding achievements for everyone, especially the students. Moreover, lastly, to develop a Development Program in Mathematics to support the improvement of the level of proficiency and academic achievement of Grade 7 students in Mathematics.

References

- Agbelele, (2010). The challenges of open learning in the developing world. International Conference on Open and distance learning. University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, March 24, 2010.
- Aguinaldo, Clemente Jr. M. (2001). "The Academic Performance of Students, Their Attitudes Toward Mathematics, and their Perceptions about the Basic Mathematics Courses and their Teachers at Philippine Normal University- Isabela Campus: A Correlational Study
- Ashcraft, M. H., and Krause, J. A. (2007). Working memory, math performance, and math anxiety. *Psychon. Bull. Rev.* 14, 243–248. doi: 10.3758/BF0319405
- Asmara Adi 2013 Kecakapan Matematis Siswa melalui Model Pembelajaran Problem Posing [Online] Available: <http://eprints.uny.ac.id/10727>
- Awofala, A. O. A & Nneji, L. M. (2011). Effect of Framing and Team Assisted Individualized Instructional Strategies on Students' Achievement in Mathematics African Journal For The Study Of Educational Issues 4(3,4) pp. 75-89
- Awofala, A.O.A. (2017). Assessing senior secondary school students' mathematical proficiency as related to gender and performance in mathematics in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 3(2), 488-502. DOI: 10.21890/ijres.327908
- Boaler, J. (2016). *Mathematical Mindsets: Unleashing Students' Potential Through Creative Math, Inspiring Messages and Innovative Teaching*. San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.
- Brooks, J. G., & Brooks, M.G. (1999). *In search of understanding: The Case for Constructivist classrooms*. Alexandria: ASCD - Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development. scholar.google.com
- Bryant, B. R., Ok, M., Kang, E. Y., Kim, M. K., Lang, R., Bryant, D. P., & Pfannestiel, K. (2015). Performance of fourth-grade students with learning disabilities on multiplication facts comparing teacher-mediated and technology-mediated interventions: A preliminary investigation. *Journal of Behavioral Education*, 24, 255-272
- Bryant, D. P. (2016). Working with your child teachers to identify and address Maths disabilities. LD online. Berch, D.B. & Mazzocco M.M.M. (2007). Why is math so hard for some children? The nature and origins general or specific deficit. *Journal of Exceptional Children Psychology* 96(3) 197-228
- Burns, M. K., Coddling, R. S., Boice, C. H., & Lukito, G. (2015). Meta-analysis of acquisition and fluency math interventions with instructional and frustration levels skills: Evidence for a skill-by-treatment interaction. *School Psychology Review*, 39(1), 69-83.
- Cherry, Kendra (2020). Background and Concept of Piaget's Theory. *International Journal of Developmental Psychology*
- Cordova, S & Tan, D. (2018). Mathematics Proficiency, Attitude, and Performance of Grade 9 Students in Private High Schools in Bukidnon, Philippines.
- DepEd K-12 Curriculum Guidelines
- Dudovskiy, John (2018). *The Ultimate Guide to Writing a Dissertation in Business Studies: A Step-by-Step Assistance*
- Ellen, Stephanie (2020). "Slovin's Formula Sampling Techniques" [sciencing.com, https://sciencing.com/slovin-formula-sampling-techniques-5475547.html](https://sciencing.com/slovin-formula-sampling-techniques-5475547.html). 25 May 2021.

- Froyd and Simpson(2010)Student- Centered Learning in a First Year UndergraduatemCourse International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research Vol. 11, No. 2, pp. 88-95, May 2015:
- Gazette., (2013). Poor junior certificate examination results. Gaborone: The BotswanaGazette.
- Geary, D. C. (2011). Cognitive predictors of individual differences in achievementgrowth mathematics: A five-year longitudinal study. *Developmental Psychology*,47, 1539-1552
- Geary, D. C., Hoard, M. K., Nugent, L., & Bailey, D. H. (2013). Adolescents' functional numeracy is predicted by their school entry number system knowledge. *PloS one*, 8 (1), e54651. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0054651
- Geary, D. C. (2013). Early foundations for mathematics learning and THE JOURNALOF SPECIAL EDUCATION APPRENTICESHIP, 5(2) 18 relations to learningdisabilities. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 22, 23-27 Harcourt, Houghton Mifflin (2020). Descriptive/Correlational Research. A Research journal
- Gray, M.(1996). Gender and mathematics. Mythology and misogyny.In E. Fennema (Ed.), *Towards gender equity in mathematics education. An ICMI Study* (pp.27–38). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers
- Harcourt, Houghton Mifflin (2020). Descriptive/Correlational Research. A Research journal
- Ibyatoba, Lyaysan;Oparina, Kseniya; Rakova, Elena (2018).Modular Approach toTeaching and Learning Grammar in Technical Universities.SOCIETY.INTEGRATION. EDUCATION Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. Volume I, May 25th -26th, 2018. 139-148
- Jaudinex, A.S. (2019). Teaching Senior High School Mathematics: Problems and Intervention. *Pegagogical Research*, 4(2), em0031. <https://doi.org.10.29333/pt/5779>
- Johnson, Anthony; Robert Kimball;Barbra Melendez,Lem Myers,Karen Rhea & Betty Travis.Pages 146-160 | Published online: 06 Mar 2009: Breaking with Tradition: Preparing Faculty to Teach in a Student- Centered or Problem Solving Environment
- Kitta, S. (2004). Enhancing Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledgeand Skills in Tanzania. Print Partners- Ipskamp: Enschede.
- Krishnan, J & Devanesan P. (2017). Identification of Problem Solving Strategies inMathematics among High School Students. Retrieved February 14, 2020 from<https://www.researchgate.net>
- Lawshe, C.H (1975). A Quantitative Approach to Content Validity. *Personnel Psychology*. 28, 563-575
- Leatham, K. R., & Peterson, B. E. (2010). Secondary mathematics cooperating teachers' perceptions of the purpose of student teaching. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 13(2), 99-119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-009-9125-0>
- M badakar C, J thakkar P, M hugar S, Kukreja P, G assudani H, Gokhale N. Evaluationof the Relevance of Piaget's Cognitive Principles among Parented and OrphanChildren in Belagavi City, Karnataka, India: A Comparative Study. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2017;10(4):346-350. doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10005-1463
- Mckean (2014) The effects of implementing student-centred learning on at-risk students'self-efficacy. Graduate Department of Curriculum, Teaching andLearning Ontario Institute for Studies in Education University of Toronto
- Middleton, Fiona (2020). The Four Types of Validity. <https://www.scribbr.com/author/Fionamiddleton>
- Ministry of Education Ghana. (2016). National training of trainers workshop forteachers of mathematics ends in Accra. Retrieved 16–09-2016, from
- M. S. DeCaro, K. E. Rotar, M. S. Kendra, and S. L. Beilock, "Diagnosing and alleviating the impact of performance pressure on mathematical problemsolving," *The Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, vol. 63, pp. 1619-1630, 2010.
- Musti-Rao, S., & Plati, E. (2015). Comparing two classwide interventions: implicationsof using technology for increasing multiplication fact fluency. *Journal of Behavioral Education*, 24(4), 418-437.
- National Center for Education Statistics. (2015). The nation's report card: Mathematics2015. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education, Institute of EducationScience. National Governors Association Center for Best Practices & Council of Chief State School Officers. (2010). *Common Core State Standards*. Washington, DC: Author
- OECD. (2016). PISA 2015 Results (Volume I): Excellence and Equity in Education.Paris: OECD Publishing.
- National Research Council. (2001). *Adding it up: Helping children learn mathematics*. J

Kilpatrick, J. Swafford, and B. Findell (Eds.). Mathematics Learning Study Committee, Center for Education, Division of Behavioral and Social Sciences and Education Washington, DC: National Academy Press. Retrieved from <http://www.nap.edu/catalog/9822.html>

Rave, Kristen; Golightly, Amy F. The Effectiveness of the Rocket Math Program for Improving Basic Multiplication Fact Fluency Education, v134 n4 p537-547 Sum 2014

Schoenfeld, A. H. (2002). Making mathematics work for all children: issues of standards, testing, and equity. *Educ. Res.* 31, 13–25. doi: 10.3102/0013189X031001013

Sharifah Fauziah Hanim Syed Zain, Farah Eliza Mohd Rasidi, Ismin Izwani Zainol Abidin(2012) Student Learning Centered in Mathematics- Constructivism In the Classroom. Volume 8. No.4

Sousa, Valmar D; Driesnack, Martha and Mendes, Isabel Amelia (2007) An overview of research designs relevant to nursing: Part 1: quantitative research designs.

Tatsuoka, K. Corter, J. & Tatsuoka, C. (2004). Patterns of Diagnosed Mathematical Content and Process Skills in TIMSS-R across a Sample of 20 Countries. *American Educational Research Journal*, 41(4), 901-926.

Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Wei, M. H., & Dzeng, H. (2014). A comparison study of math education and math performance between Asian countries and the United States. *Journal of Socialomics*, 3(02), 2167-0358. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2167-0358.1000111>

Wheelan, C. (2014). *Naked Statistics*. W. W. Norton & Company. <https://www.statisticshowto.com/probability-and-statistics/sampling-in-statistics/stratified-random-sample/>

Wibrowski CR, Matthews WK, Kitsantas A. The role of a skills learning support program on first-generation college students' self-regulation, motivation, and academic achievement: a longitudinal study. *J Coll Stud Retent.* 2017;19(3):317–32.

Whittington, A., & Grey, N. (2014). Mastering metacompetence: The science and art of cognitive behavioural therapy. In A. Whittington & N. Grey (Eds.), *How to become a more effective CBT therapist: Mastering metacompetence in clinical practice* (pp. 3–16). Wiley Blackwell

Yadav (2017) *International Reserach Journal of Mathematics, Engineering and IT*, Vol.4, Issue 1

Zakaria, Effandi and Zanaton Iksan(2017) Promoting Cooperative learning in Science and Mathematics Education: A Malaysian Perspective. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 2007, 3(1), 35-39

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Riza S. Berrame

Javier Laxina I Memorial High School
Department of Education – Philippines